

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: FBCD

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"Let's meet!" Event Validation Report – Denmark

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Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of FBCD for the organisation and validation of the Gaardbageriet event in Region Midtjylland in Denmark on March 28, 2023. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the producer event in Region Midtjylland in Denmark.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

A Producers event with focus on SFSC has been selected:

Bagekursus/Baking course on March 28, 2023 at a farm bakery in Ringkøbing in Denmark.

Hotels, cafés, and small producers have been invited to develop their own dough recipe, baking different kinds of bread and learning about different types of flour from a local producer (farmer and miller) and optional supply possibilities directly from Gyldenlund. Sustainable handling of the bread in their own businesses was part of the programme.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Start of the day	Registration and welcome Introduction to agroBRIDGES Presentation of Gaardbageren	09:00 – 10:00	Ringkøbing, Denmark
The baking course	Make your own sourdough Stir a basic dough Learn to further develop recipes Baking techniques How to make technical and commercial value	10:00 – 13:30	Ringkøbing, Denmark
SFSC	Lunch Presentation on types of flour and raw materials Short Food Supply Chains	13:30 – 15:00	Ringkøbing, Denmark
Exchanges of information	Sustainable handling of the bread in their own businesses was discussed. The exchanges of information between the participants were plentiful and beneficial.	All day	Ringkøbing, Denmark

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The farm bakery, which is in a very remote rural area near the west coast, was established a year ago after the mink production on the farm was closed due to the Covid-19 situation in Denmark. An idea quickly grew that they should use their barn and furriery building for something else. The owner of the farm bakery was already a baker by training, but no longer actively pursued this career until they started the farm bakery. Today they employ one full-time baker, 5-6 temps, and some young girls are part-time in the shop/café. They produce 6 days a week and bake both for business and private customers.

The bread and cakes are sold directly to consumers and food service in 3 different SFSCs:

1. The combined shop and café is open Friday and Saturday
2. Self-service/door sales is open Wednesday, Thursday, and Saturday (fresh and frozen products)
3. Webshop: Click 'n Collect (orders can be collected in self-service/door sales in the farm bakery and in two small villages in the area on Saturdays).

Figure 1: The shop & café and the self-service/door sales

The farm bakery buys flour directly from Gyldenlund, which is a farmer milling and selling their own crop-based products directly to producers, food service and consumers. The owner was invited to participate and explain the quality of the different flours and their work with different crops to develop their product portfolio.

Timeline:

5 weeks before the event the invitation was ready for distribution on web and social media, and for direct mail to a list of potential participants. Posts were ongoing and share on LinkedIn.

Later on, a week before the event a reminder was in a newsletter.

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Project manager	1	Development of promo material	In-house	1 person day
Project manager	1	Development of the event concept including the agreement with the farm bakery and the miller	In-house	1 person days
Project manager	1 - 2	Promotion of the event	In-house	1 person days
Project manager	1	Administration and practical tasks	In-house	1 person days
Baker + miller	2	Preparations for the event	In-house	2 person days
Catering	1	Food and drinks for guests	In-house	0.5 person day
Manager	1	Support of the promotion process by “colleague” in the local business service center	External	2 person days

2.4 Event material

Invitation including GDPR statement/acceptance, event programme, social media and list of participants (here anonymised) have been produced according to the suggestions in the guidelines.

Figure 2: Event material

Information om GDPR *

Jeg accepterer GDPR betingelser

Ved tilmelding til dette event er jeg informeret om, at Food & Bio Cluster Denmark opbevarer oplysninger om mig i sit kunderegister. Oplysningerne anvendes udelukkende i forbindelse med de aktiviteter, Food & Bio Cluster Denmark udfører for mig som medlem eller deltager. Jeg accepterer samtidig, at Food & Bio Cluster Denmark må kontakte mig vedrørende andre relevante, faglige arrangementer, muligheder og evaluering. Ligeledes er jeg opmærksom på, at nogle af mine oplysninger vil blive delt (navn og organisation) i forbindelse med udlevering af en deltagerliste til deltagerne, til donorer, til afholdelsesstedet og til oplægsholdere på det arrangement jeg er tilmeldt. Ved at tilmelde mig dette arrangement accepterer jeg, at der kan blive taget billeder eller optaget video til brug i markedsføringen af Food & Bio Cluster Denmark. Se vores datapolitik på www.foodbiocluster.dk.

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

With focus on the one of the two Danish priority sectors, cereals it was obvious to include two successful farmers having lately extended their farming business to a business with a closer connection to their customers. Both very successful with SFSC.

Both the farm baker and the farm miller were easy to recruit and involve in the process with the development of the event, as they both believe in sharing their knowledge with other companies and at the same time could interact with potential customers and potential candidates for a future network.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The strategy has been to invited hotels, cafes, restaurants and other small producers in the local area and in the region, but also to handpick some of them by sending direct mails and contact them on phone and at other meetings with the support of the local business service center.

Figure 3: Event online communications

The poster is for a 'BAGEKURSUS' (Baking Course) held on 28 March 2023 from 9:00 to 15:00. It is organized by Food & Bio Cluster Denmark and agr BRIDGES. The course is free but has a 500 DKK no-show fee. It focuses on rye bread and sourdough. The location is Gaardbageren in Ringkøbing. The poster includes a 'TILMELD DIG HER' (Sign up here) button and a list of benefits for signing up, such as meeting local producers and creating a network. It also mentions that the course is supported by the European Union.

Food & Bio Cluster
Denmark

BAGEKURSUS

- med råvarer direkte fra producenten

28 marts 2023
9:00 – 15:00

**TILMELD
DIG HER**

Dette bagekursus er for dig der sælger/bruger brød, enten i din gårdbutik, din cafe eller på din restaurant og gerne vil i gang med at bage selv, eller blive inspireret til nye metoder og opskrifter.

På kurset vil vi have fokus på rugbrød og brød bagt på surdej. Vi bager med mel fra [Evidentland](#).

HVORFOR TILMELDE SIG?

- Du kommer tæt på produkter fra din egen region
- Vi har fokus på korte forsyningskæder
- Lær at lave din egen surdej
- Få tips og tricks til lækkert bagværk
- Mød en lokal ildsjæl
- Skab nyt netværk

Deltagelse er gratis, men på grund af begrænsede antal pladser er der et no-show gebyr på 500,- kr.

Gaardbageren står for dagens forplejning, så vi får også mulighed for at smage Camilla's søde bagværk.

Sidste frist for tilmelding er tirsdag den 21. marts 2023.

agr
BRIDGES
Funded by
the European Union

Gaardbageren
Korbæk 17
8950 Ringkøbing

Gaardbageren

Læs mere her: www.agrbridges.eu og følg os på [in](#)

Bagekursus

Workshop

Sted
Gaardbageren, Nørbæk 17, 6950 Ringkøbing, Danmark

Pris
Gratis / 1750

Fra
20. marts 2023 kl. 09:00

Til
28. marts 2023 kl. 15:00

Kontakt

Conny Hanghøj
c3@foodbiocluster.dk
33090000

20. marts 2023

Dette bagekursus er for dig der sælger brød, enten i din gårdbutik, din cafe eller på din restaurant og gerne vil i gang med at bage selv, eller blive inspireret til nye metoder og opskrifter. På kurset vil vi have fokus på rugbrød og brød bage på surdej. Vi bager med mel fra øjstenlund.

HYVORFOR TILVELDE SIG?

- Du kommer tæt på produkter fra din egen region
- Vi har fokus på korn fornyingskæder
- Lær at lave din egen surdej
- På tips og tricks til lækkert bagværk
- Vag en lokal forløb
- Skab nyt netværk

Deltagelse er gratis, men på grund af begrænsede antal pladser er der et no-show gebyr på 500,- kr.

Gaardbageren står for dagens forplejning, så vi får også mulighed for at smage Camillas søde bagværk.

Funded by the European Union

Food & Bio Cluster Denmark er den landsdækkende klyngeorganisation for fødevarer og bioressourcer i Danmark. Vi er den samlede platform for innovation og vækst i klyngen - for danske og internationale virksomheder og vidensinstitutioner.

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Agro Food Park 13
4200 Århus N
Tlf: 3366 2000
CVR: 29682070
fb@foodbiocluster.dk

GOLD

Cluster Management Excellence

2022-2023

Adresser til øvrige kontaktpunkter

20. marts 2023

Deltag i Food & Bio Cluster Denmark's events og få spændende inspiration og ny viden fra den danske og internationale fødevarer- og bioressourcescene.

Bagekursus
28. marts
[Læs mere og tilmeld dig her](#)

Start Up Food Reg 23 - Emballage og lovgivning 3 af 4 ARHUS
29. marts
[Læs mere og tilmeld dig her](#)

Net Zero Pathways 2023
30. marts
[Læs mere og tilmeld dig her](#)

Plant2Food kick-off
30. marts
[Læs mere og tilmeld dig her](#)

Online Food Dating
30. marts
[Læs mere og tilmeld dig her](#)

Start Up Food Reg 23 - Kommunikation og rettigheder 4 af 4
13. april
[Læs mere og tilmeld dig her](#)

Innovation in biosolutions - Reaching the next level
13. april

20.12

← bagekursus

Personer
Indlæg
Job
Virksomheder

Indlæg

Conny Hanghøj · 1

Senior Innovation Manager hos Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
Videorulet fra Conny Hanghøj · 2u ·

KOM FRISK

Der er stadig få ledige pladser
Gårdbageren, Food & Bio Cluster Denmark og AgroBridges Project 2021-2023 inviterer til bagekursus

Bagekursus
foodbiocluster.dk · 1 min, læsetid

20.19

← Artikler, indlæg m.m.

Al aktivitet
Artikler
Indlæg
Dokumenter

Conny Hanghøj · 1

Senior Innovation Manager hos Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
1md. · Reageret ·

Dremer du om at bage lækker brød til dine kunder?
Hvad med at kunne servere godt hjemmebagt rugbrød og surdejsbrød på menukortet?
Bruge gode danske råvarer med kort forsyningskæde?

Nu er der en chance for at få pudset bageteknikkerne af!

Vi inviterer cafeer, gårdbutikker og restauranter til bagekursus
Tirsdag den 28. marts 2023 fra kl. 9-15
Hos: Gaardbageren, Nørbæk 17, 6950 Ringkøbing

Der er begrænset antal pladser, så det er først til mølle 🙌

Se mere og tilmeld dig her

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The event was implemented according to the programme and the participants exchange knowledge very freely, as they were a relatively small group. They all had interest in SFSC and sustainable development of their business. There was a request for establishing a future network to support the future development of their businesses and general inspiration.

Figure 4: Materials and dough

Figure 5: Event organisation

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	2
Food service combined with retail/shop	3
Hotel	1
Support cluster	2
Total	8

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Question #1: Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	3				3	
Question #2: Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	5			1		
Question #3: Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local producers, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	5		1			
Question #4: Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local producers' food, various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	1	3	2			
Question #5: Did you find enough information about how and where to buy local food from the producers or other businesses you've met?	5		1			
Question #6: Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?		2	4			

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

Yes, it is a fine way to get familiar with other producers, restaurants, cafes etc. (future networking) and to support each other’s business by using cereal/flour directly from the farmer/miller. The use of the different templates is an efficient way to make professional-looking invitations and other communication material for the event.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, maybe twice a year. If necessary, we would adjust the event e.g. if we would invite a different target group.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, we used the templates for the invitation, programme, participants list, and social media.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the event was tailored both to our needs and the needs of the participants.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Most owners of small businesses are very busy, and some cannot afford to hire a replacement, allowing them to attend events.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

I would be nice to have access to free photos for the invitation and other communication materials.

Networking is very important for farmers/small producers who spend most of their time working at home with their own business, therefore it would be nice if networking could be included more actively in the guidelines e.g. time for networking during the events or time for organizing future networking activities among the participants.